

From poo to precision: AI-powered colorectal cancer detection

David S. Foster, Cerys A. Mitchell, Nerissa E. Thomas, Charles D. Brilliant, Adam I. Nixon, Nafiseh Badiei, Peter R. Dunstan and Dean A. Harris

CanSense, Institute of Life Sciences 2, Swansea University. Swansea SA2 8PP, UK
david.foster@cansenseltd.com

Abstract. Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the second highest cause of cancer deaths per year and was responsible for 935K deaths in 2020 globally. 1.9M new CRC cases are diagnosed each year, expected to rise to 3.2M by 2040. CRC detection pathways predominantly use faecal immunochemical test (FIT) followed by colonoscopy. Although FIT is inexpensive and has reasonable sensitivity for colorectal cancer it is also elevated in benign conditions and has poor capability for detection of high-risk adenomas. Additionally, uptake of FIT is suboptimal and the test may be contributing to widening disparities in cancer detection among underserved communities¹.

CanSense-CRC is the first commercial use of Raman spectroscopy combined with AI to detect changes in serum specific to colorectal cancer. Unlabelled serum metabolites from aberrant lipid/protein energy substrate pathways are excited by laser light to produce a spectral output akin to a biological 'fingerprint'. A machine-learning algorithm, forms software as a medical device that classifies the spectra arising from patient serum to rapidly inform clinicians the likelihood of colorectal cancer being present.

As a breakthrough AI-based test, CanSense-CRC moves the needle towards improved cancer survival through early cancer stage analyte detection in line with the NHS Long Term Plan ambition to detect 75% of cancers at stage I/II by 2028. The CanSense-CRC test has the potential to rebalance the current socioeconomic inequality around testing in the UK and other countries with cancer detection challenges where colonoscopy resources are limited and by offering an alternative to faecal testing.

Keywords: AI driven early diagnosis and prevention, Colorectal cancer, Spectroscopy.

References

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